

SEARCH FOR NEW ANTIBACTERIAL COMPOUNDS. PART II.
EVALUATION OF THE ANTIBACTERIAL
ACTIVITY OF NEW PHENOLS

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The bacteriostatic activity of 2-alkyl-3-methyl-6-*tert.*-butylphenols and 2-alkyl-4-*tert.*-butyl-6-chlorophenols against various bacteria has been determined. Three phenols, found to be comparatively active, have been evaluated for their Rideal-Walker coefficients.

In the cases of xylenols, the germicidal activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* increases more rapidly with branched chain compounds, and in the cases of dihydroxy derivatives, branched chain compounds have been reported to possess unusually high activity (Baichwal, Jhavery and Khorana, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1951, 10, 498). Klarmann, Sternov and Gates (*J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1933, 19, 835; 1934, 20, 40) showed that *para*-alkyl derivatives of *ortho*-chlorophenols were efficient germicides. Hence, various 2-alkyl-3-methyl-6-*tert.*-butylphenols (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 79) and 2-alkyl-4-*tert.*-butyl-6-chlorophenols (*ibid.*, 1956, 33, 211) have been tested for their bacteriostatic action against *Streptococcus haemolyticus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas pyocyaneus* and *Salmonella typhi* or *Bacillus subtilis*, following the procedure of Mukerji (*Ind. Med. Gazz.*, 1954, 89, 415) at the dilutions of 1/100, 1/500, 1/1000, 1/2000, 1/5000 and 1/10,000 in 3% agar medium.

Bean and Berry (*J. Pharmacol.*, 1951, 3, 639, 55) have found that the maximum activity of a halogenated phenol, solubilised by aqueous soap solution, is exhibited at the critical concentration of the soap. The activity of the halogenated phenol is related to its concentration in the micelles of soap and is independent of the overall concentration. In the experiments reported here, the colloidal agar served more or less the same purpose as the soap micelles. It is postulated that under these circumstances the bacteria are affected by the way of the Donnan membrane. The semipermeable bacterial wall with its own surface charge acts as a membrane and exchange occurs between phenol presented to the bacteria by the agar or the soap micelle and the inner substances within the bacteria.

2-Butyl-3-methyl-6-*tert.*-butylphenol, 2-butyl-4-*tert.*-butyl-6-chlorophenol and 2-octyl-4-*tert.*-butyl-6-chlorophenol have been found to be active against *S. haemolyticus* and *S. aureus* even in dilutions between 1/5000 and 1/10,000. Hence, these were evaluated for their Rideal-Walker coefficients.

TABLE I

Bacteriostatic activity of phenols.

No.	Phenols.		<i>Strep. haem.</i>	<i>Staph. aur.</i>	<i>Pseudo. pyoc.</i>	<i>Sal. typhi.</i>	<i>Bac. subtil.</i>
1.	2-Ethyl-P	No growth	1/1000	1/1000	1/500	1/1000	...
		Growth	1/2000	1/2000	1/1000	1/2000	1/100(T)
2.	2-Propyl-P	No growth	1/2000	1/1000	1/500	1/500	1/100
		Growth	...	1/2000(T)	1/1000	1/1000	...
3.	2-Butyl-P	No growth	1/5000	1/5000	1/1000	1/2000	...
		Growth	1/10,000(T)	1/10,000	1/2000	1/5000	1/100(T)
4.	2-Hexyl-P	No growth	1/1000	1/1000	...	...	...
		Growth	1/2000(T)	1/2000(T)	1/100	1/100	1/100(T)
5.	2-Heptyl-P	No growth	1/1000	1/1000	...	...	...
		Growth	1/2000	1/2000	1/100	1/100	1/100(T)
6.	2-Decyl-P	No growth	1/1000	1/1000	1/100	1/500	1/100
		Growth	1/2000(T)	1/2000(T)	1/500	1/1000	...
7.	2-Dodecyl-P	No growth	1/2000	1/500	...	1/500	...
		Growth	...	1/1000	1/100	1/1000	1/100(T)
8.	2-Ethyl-F	No growth	1/1000	1/1000	1/100	1/1000	...
		Growth	1/2000	1/2000	1/500	1/2000	1/100(T)
9.	2-Propyl-F	No growth	1/2000	1/500	...	1/1000	...
		Growth	...	1/1000	1/100	1/2000	1/100(T)
10.	2-Butyl-F	No growth	1/5000	1/5000	...	1/5000	...
		Growth	1/10,000	1/10,000	1/100(T)	1/10,000	1/100
11.	2-Pentyl-F	No growth	1/2000	1/1000	...	...	1/100
		Growth	1/5000	1/2000	1/100	1/100	...
12.	2-Hexyl-F	No growth	1/500	1/100	1/100	1/400	1/100
		Growth	1/1000(T)	1/500	1/500	1/500	...
13.	2-Octyl-F	No growth	1/5000	1/5000	...	...	1/100
		Growth	1/10,000	1/10,000	1/100	1/100	...
14.	2-Decyl-F	No growth	1/500	1/100	...	...	1/100
		Growth	1/1000(T)	1/500	1/100	1/100	...
15.	2-Dodecyl-F	No growth	1/500	1/1000	...	...	1/100
		Growth	1/1000	1/2000(T)	1/100	1/100	...
16.	P.	No growth	1/1000	1/100	...	...	1/100
		Growth	1/2000	1/500	1/100	1/100	...
17.	F.	No growth	1/500	1/100	...	...	1/100
		Growth	1/1000(T)	1/500	1/100	1/100	...
18.	Phenol	No growth	1/500	1/100	1/1000	1/500	...
		Growth	1/1000	1/500	1/2000	1/1000	...

P = 3-methyl-6-tert.-butylphenol.

F = 4-tert.-butyl-6-chlorophenol

T = growth in traces.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Evaluation of Bacteriostatic Activity.—The phenols were dispersed in the molten agar medium at about 50° by thorough shaking at a concentration of 1/100. Further dilutions were made from these in the same medium and poured in 3 inch petri dishes in 20 c.c. amounts and immediately placed in a refrigerator for setting. After about an hour these were placed in an incubator at 37° overnight. At the same time sub-cultures of different pathogenic organisms, viz., *S. haemolyticus*, *S. aureus*, *P. pyocyaneus*, *S. typhi* and *B. subtilis* were made on solid media and incubated. Next day suspensions from these sub-cultures were made in normal saline so as to contain approximately thousand million organisms per c.c. From these streak cultures were made on the above nutrient agar containing phenols under test. These were incubated at 37° for 48 hours and the results noted at the end of 24 and 48 hours. If a phenol appeared to be inactive at a certain dilution against most of the bacteria, tests in further dilutions were not carried out. Tests with *B. subtilis* were conducted only with 1/100 dilution and next it was replaced by *S. typhi*. The results are summarised in Table I.

Rideal-Walker Coefficients.—The phenols (0.1 c.c. each, mixed with one drop of Turkey Red oil) were used for preparing various dilutions in distilled water. Three dilutions of each phenol in 10 c.c. aliquots were taken in small Erlenmeyer flasks and placed on water-baths, maintained at 20°, along with carbolic acid in the dilutions 1/115 and 1/120. *S. typhi*, maintained in a standard way, was sub-cultured in the nutrient broth (p_n 7.2) for 24 hours at 37°. It was employed in this test after standardising it with the same broth to contain approximately five hundred million organisms per c.c. Culture suspensions of 0.2 c.c. of *S. typhi* were successively added with a pipette in each of the five flasks with an interval of half a minute. With a standard platinum loop having an internal diameter of 4 mm, transfers were made successively every half a minute in 5 c.c. amounts of ordinary nutrient broth, till four such transfers were made, allowing a maximum contact period of 10 minutes in each dilution of the phenol. Subsequently the test tubes containing the cultured broth were placed in an incubator and the growth of the bacteria was observed after a period of 24 hours. The results are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Phenols.	R.W. coeff.
1.	2-Octyl-4-tert.-butyl-6-chloro-phenol	2.6
2.	2-Butyl-4-tert.-butyl-6-chloro- ,	2.6
3.	2-Butyl-3-methyl-6-tert. butyl- ,,	6.5

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